

DELIVERABLE 5.7

FIRST UPDATED VERSION OF THE COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

ICLEI ES
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First updated version of the communication and dissemination plan

A revision of the first version of the FoodCLIC Communication and Dissemination Plan (D5.2, submitted in 2023) led to the creation of this document, which constitutes the 'First updated version of the communication and dissemination plan' (D5.7). A 'History of Changes' that contributed to the creation of the updated version can be found in Annex 1.

A second updated version (D5.10) will be provided in project month 36.

1. BACKGROUND

FoodCLIC:

FoodCLIC will bridge connections between information, planning and food policy processes to contribute to the [European Green Deal](#) priorities, the [Farm-to-Fork strategy](#) and the EU's Climate ambition for [2030](#) and [2050](#) as well as the [Food 2030 Agenda](#). Stakeholders' engagement in food systems governance, will be increased through the creation and enhancement of Food Policy Networks (FPNs) that work with Living Labs (LLs), and long-term involvement of Higher Education Institutes (HEIs) and Research Organizations (ROs).

The project uses an innovative and integrated framework (the CLIC) to guide policy-, planning- and practice-based interventions in urban food environments (and associated urban food systems) that deliver sustainability Co-benefits, establish spatial Linkages between rural and urban areas, Include all food stakeholders, and build Connectivities with other relevant stakeholders and policy fields outside the food domain.

In practice, FoodCLIC will conduct more than 30 interventions in local food environments and interrelated food systems, support and foster the development of integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks across at least 45 European cities and towns in order to establish strong interfaces between science, policy and practice. The project will also develop the first network of Higher Education Institutes committed to the sustainability of urban food systems. The project will establish a Food Policy Network platform and a Knowledge Hub.

FoodCLIC – Communication & Dissemination:

The communication and dissemination of the project will support FoodCLIC to realise these ambitions by raising awareness about the topic, sharing project findings and engaging the target audiences to utilise the project's outputs.

In this sense, this document, the FoodCLIC Communication and Dissemination Plan, outlines the project's approach to communication and dissemination action. The aim of this plan is to guide

project partners in their efforts and to steer relevant communication and dissemination actions of all members of the project consortium. Therefore, this document provides its readers with:

- information on FoodCLIC's main target audiences,
- key messages for external communications,
- guidelines on FoodCLIC's visual identity and the acknowledgement of the EU funding,
- indicators of how communication and dissemination activities will be monitored.

FoodCLIC – Broadening, Exploitation & Advocacy:

The 'Broadening plan on extension city-regions' (D5.6) developed at M16 complements this plan. The Broadening plan facilitates the sharing, dialogue, translation and context-based adoption of good practices and lessons learned with eight additional city-regions. Furthermore, it supports transferability and replicability of FoodCLIC outputs in eight additional city-regions. Broadening activities, including peer-to-peer exchanges, will be highlighted in communication and dissemination events. The Broadening city-regions will join the FoodCLIC network in order to gain support for developing a vision and strategy for food system work in their city-region and visibility for local measures and strategies. In turn, the consortium will expand its impact through the Broadening city-regions.

The 'Exploitation Plan' (M9, D5.4) was developed to make FoodCLIC's results usable for a wide range of stakeholders. The FoodCLIC process, outlined in the Broadening plan (D5.6), will also be considered as an exploitable result of the project.

Communication and dissemination activities are aligned with the project's 'Advocacy plan for interaction with higher level authorities' (D4.1), coordinated by ICLEI ES as Task 4.2 leader. FoodCLIC's advocacy pitches and talking points contribute to the overall KPIs defined in this plan. Similarly, the advocacy messages are integrated into the communication and dissemination measures and channels.

2. BASICS

In general, **communication activities** will convey key messages about FoodCLIC's results and provide information on its structure, objectives, mission and the partners involved. **Dissemination activities** will share more in-depth lessons from the mapping of FPNs (WP2), the real-life interventions (WP3), the training and monitoring activities (WP1) and the analysis of the replication potential of integrated food policies (WP4) to facilitate the spread of FoodCLIC's best practices and solutions (WP4-5).¹ Content management and distribution will take place throughout the

¹ See also European Commission, "[Communication, dissemination and exploitation – What is the difference and why they all matter?](#)"

duration of the project to maintain a high level of attention. News items, articles and social media posts will be regularly produced and distributed through the project and partner channels.

2.1 BRANDING

Branding, i.e. the visual identity for FoodCLIC was developed by project month 4 (December 2022), with the designer commissioned by an external contractor. Key element of the FoodCLIC visual identity is the FoodCLIC logo (see figure 1). The logo goes along with a defined colour scheme and assigned fonts, creating a brand concept with recognition effect.

Apart from that, the branding entails logo variations, templates for (Microsoft) Office applications, templates for leaflets, posters and other dissemination materials, social media visual templates, simple visuals and animated icons for use and website elements. Project partners are asked to adhere to these brand elements in external communications, i.e. when creating public documents, graphic material etc.

Additionally, Article 17.2 of the Grant Agreement obliges all members of the project team to acknowledge the EU support received across all communication and dissemination activities of the beneficiaries related to the action.

Figure 1: FoodCLIC logo

Detailed and easy to use guidelines for project partners on how to apply and adhere to the FoodCLIC visual identity and on how to acknowledge the EU funding correctly and visibly by displaying the European flag (emblem) and funding statement were provided in a separate guiding document, the “**FoodCLIC Design Style Guide**”, for project partners and relevant external stakeholders in the month of December 2022 (project month 4). Project partners with access to the project internal SharePoint area, can access the Style Guide [here](#).

Complementarily, the European Research Executive Agency provides further instructions that can be accessed [here](#).

2.2 BRANDING APPLIED: EXAMPLES

The materials listed below have been created and serve as examples for project partners. All materials were made available to the project partners on the project's internal SharePoint platform. Project partners with access to the project internal SharePoint area, can access the files by clicking on the provided link.

Figure 2: Branding applied, examples

- Roll-up banner: [view here](#)
- Microsoft Office Templates: [view here](#)
- Posters: [view here](#)
- Project Presentation: [view here](#)
- Infographics / Visualizations: [view here](#)
- Handouts, leaflets and flyers: [view here](#)
- Project business cards: [view here](#)
- CLIC icons: [view here](#)

2.3 MONITORING

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) were defined to facilitate performance tracking and monitoring of accomplishments in the area of communication and dissemination.

All KPIs are listed in the table below and repeated in the relevant section of this document. Additionally, the table below prepares for the reporting to the European Commission, by providing further information on each KPI.

To better oversee each project partner's contribution to each of these KPIs and to keep track of all partners' dissemination and communication activities and efforts, an [online tracking tool](#) is provided by ICLEI Europe (ICLEI ES). **All project partners are requested to contribute to FoodCLIC's overall communication and dissemination efforts and to report on their activities through the provided [tool](#).** Column "Tracking" of the table below provides helpful indications for the project partners of how the provided [tracking tool](#) should be used for documentation purposes. ICLEI ES will rely on project partners' inputs and take care of compiling and keeping track of all communication and dissemination efforts to facilitate the reporting to the European Commission.

KPI	Reporting of communication (C) and dissemination (D) activities to the European Commission:					TRACKING
	C	D	ACTIVITY	DESCRIPTION	EXPECTED OUTCOME	
Visual identity Milestone 8, due in month 4, ICLEI ES	x		Visual identity created and continuously applied	The project's visual identity is defined (by project month 4) and applied by all project partners throughout the entire project duration.	FoodCLIC's visual identity is defined (by project month 4) and applied by all project partners throughout the entire project duration.	ICLEI ES will monitor the implementation and application of FoodCLIC's visual identity and support project partners on an individual basis.
Online project website / platform (48+ blogs, 100+ project outputs, audience 1,000,000+) D5.3, due in month 7, ICLEI ES	x		Set-up of the FoodCLIC project website D5.3, due in month 7, ICLEI ES	ICLEI ES will set up the project website and make it accessible online.	The (initial version of the) project website is online by project month seven.	Verification through D5.3.
		x	Maintenance of the FoodCLIC project website, including regular publications, e.g. of web articles, project results and news items.	ICLEI ES takes care of the website maintenance with the aim of increasing the project's visibility and providing visitors with up-to-date project information. At least 48+ blogs and 100+ project outputs will be published on the project website.	Through the regular publication of content (48+ blogs and 100+ project outputs) on the project website, an audience of > 1,000,000 stakeholders will be reached. The website will be left online as a repository after project end (unmaintained).	ICLEI ES will manage and maintain the project website, and monitor the achievement of this KPI.
FoodCLIC Social Media accounts (200+ posts on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn etc.; audience 80,000+)	x		Set-up of the central FoodCLIC Social Media accounts	ICLEI ES will set up the central FoodCLIC Social Media account(s).	The FoodCLIC Social Media accounts for central communication are defined and launched.	The central FoodCLIC Social Media accounts will be set up and managed by ICLEI ES. ICLEI ES monitors the achievement of these KPIs.
		x	Regular publications on the central FoodCLIC Social Media accounts	ICLEI ES maintains the project's social media channel(s) with the aim of increasing the project's visibility and providing its network with up-to-date project information and insights.	Through regular publications of content on FoodCLIC's central Social Media channels (at least 200 posts on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Mastodon, YouTube or similar), an audience of > 80,000 stakeholders will be reached (measured in impressions).	Project partners are requested to report on their FoodCLIC-related communication activities on Social Media by selecting "Type of activity: Social Media" and submitting additional information in the provided fields of the tracking tool .

<p>16+ short videos/ vlogs (YouTube, project website; audience 5,000+)</p> <p>D5.11, Due in month 46, ICLEI ES</p>	x		<p>Videos on FoodCLIC's city-regions.</p>	<p>Short videos/ vlogs will be produced to feature effective solutions applied in the food environments of the eight city-regions (D5.11).</p>	<p>16+ short videos/ vlogs will be produced and published on YouTube and/ or the project website to reach an audience of > 5,000 stakeholders.</p>	<p>ICLEI ES monitors the achievement of this target.</p>
<p>50+ flyers, banners, posters and infographics</p>		x	<p>Visual material</p>	<p>Dissemination material, such as flyers, banners, posters and infographics will be created by ICLEI ES and project partners to visually engage stakeholders.</p>	<p>50+ flyers, banners, posters and infographics will be created.</p> <p>All materials are stored in the project's internal Microsoft Teams environment, and the materials relevant to external stakeholders are made available for download on the website.</p>	<p>All project partners will contribute to the achievement of this target. Monitoring takes place through the established tracking tool.</p> <p>Project partners are requested to document their contribution to this KPI by selecting "Type of activity: Visual material (flyer, poster, banner, infographic, leaflet ...)" in the tracking tool.</p>
<p>50+ messages on ICLEI's and Metropolis' mailing list (audience 37,000+)</p>	x	(x)	<p>E-mailings</p>	<p>Project updates, activities and outcomes will be regularly promoted through features in the ICLEI Europe, ICLEI Global, ICLEI Africa newsletters, the organizations' topical newsletters and Metropolis' mailings to external stakeholders.</p>	<p>Inclusion of 50+ FoodCLIC related messages in mailings sent out via ICLEI's and Metropolis' mailing channels to reach an audience of at least 37,000 stakeholders.</p>	<p>All project partners will contribute to the achievement of this target. Monitoring takes place through the established tracking tool.</p> <p>Project partners are requested to document their contribution to this KPI by selecting "Type of activity: Emailing and Newsletters" in the tracking tool.</p> <p>Particularly, ICLEI Europe, ICLEI Global, ICLEI Africa and Metropolis are asked to contribute to the achievement of this KPI.</p>
<p>10+ articles (news items) and/ or press releases</p>	x	(x)	<p>Articles (news items) and press releases</p>	<p>At least 10 articles (news items) and/ or press releases will be produced and distributed through different identified channels throughout the project lifetime.</p>	<p>10+ published articles (news items) and/ or press releases.</p>	<p>All project partners will contribute to the achievement of this target. Monitoring takes place through the established tracking tool.</p>

						Project partners are requested to document their contribution to this KPI by selecting "Type of activity: Press article/ release" or "Type of activity: Web article/ Web publication / Media article" in the tracking tool .
Open access national and international articles (15+ popular articles, 15+ scientific articles)		x	Popular articles and scientific articles	The dissemination of FoodCLIC's results entails the publication of open access (scientific) articles on a national and international level.	Publication of 15+ popular articles and 15+ scientific articles.	All project partners will contribute to the achievement of this target. Monitoring takes place through the established tracking tool. Project partners are requested to document their contribution to this KPI by selecting "Type of activity: Scientific article" in the tracking tool .
6 FoodCLIC e-newsletters (audience 1,500+)	(x)	x	Newsletter	External stakeholders will be provided with the opportunity to register for the FoodCLIC e-newsletter, which will be sent out at least 6 times throughout the project duration.	Sent out of 6 FoodCLIC e-newsletters to reach an audience of 1,500+ stakeholders (i.e. at least 250 subscribers).	ICLEI ES manages the newsletter subscription process and is responsible for the development and sent-out of 6 FoodCLIC newsletters. ICLEI ES monitors the achievement of this target.
Presentations at events (15+ presentations at international conferences (audience 750+, i.e. 50 per event); 80+ presentations at events in the partner city-regions (audience 10,000+))		x	Presentations at events (e.g. conferences)	Project partners who are provided with the opportunity to present the FoodCLIC project (results) at events, meetings or conferences, will contribute to the increased visibility of the project.	15+ presentations at international conferences (audience 750+, i.e. 50 per event); 80+ presentations at events in the partner city-regions (audience 10,000+).	All project partners will contribute to the achievement of this target. Monitoring takes place through the established tracking tool. Project partners are requested to document their contribution to this KPI by selecting "Type of activity: - Event Participation at as FoodCLIC representative - Event Presentation of FoodCLIC - Event Organization of a (FoodCLIC) event (e.g.

						workshop, meeting, webinar, exhibition,...)" in the tracking tool . An event can be a conference, workshop, webinar, meeting or else.
2 conferences - 1 mid-term (mid-term international workshop), Milestone 27, due in month 26, ICLEI ES - 1 final high-level conference, Milestone 38, due in month 53, ICLEI ES	(x)	x	Conferences	A mid-term international workshop + a final international conference will be organized to disseminate key findings and stimulate the uptake of FoodCLIC's strategies and tools. A short report to communicate the main outcomes of the events will be published on the project website. (= Conference report).		ICLEI ES monitors the achievement of this target.
Promotion of WP1 D1.7 - Online toolkit 300+ downloads/ users/ visits	x		Promotion of key project deliverables	Key project deliverables, which are reporting on valuable project results, will be promoted to push their dissemination. These deliverables are: - D1.7 Online toolkit - guidelines and tools for mappings, real-life interventions, RMDE framework and training (VU, M 54) - D2.1 Report on facilitators of, and barriers to development and implementation of evidence-based and integrated food policies and planning frameworks (SURREY, M6) - D2.2 Report on food-related policies and planning frameworks and initiatives in the 8 city-regions and at national level (ICLEI ES, M10) - D4.6 Four policy	300+ downloads/ users/ visits	ICLEI ES monitors the achievement of these targets.
Promotion of WP2 D2.2 - Report on access to sustainable and healthy food 200+ downloads users/ visits					200+ downloads/ users/ visits	
Promotion of WP2 D2.1 - Report on integrated food policies and planning frameworks; 200+ downloads/ users/ visits					By promoting key project deliverables and their content, i.e. project results and derived policy recommendations etc. 200+ downloads/ users/ visits	
Promotion of WP4 D4.6 - 4 policy briefs; Audience 5,000+					Audience 5,000+	

Dissemination of WP5 D5.8 and D5.13 - 30 practice abstracts; 30 uploads to EIP-AGRI			briefs for higher level public authorities - D5.8 and D5.13 practice abstracts (ICLEI ES, M18 + M54).	30 uploads to EIP-AGRI	
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2.4 GENDER

All FoodCLIC communications use gender-sensitive language and imagery in line with the [European Institute for Gender Equality’s Toolkit on gender-sensitive communication](#). The Ethics Advisory Committee (EAC) established in FoodCLIC will be consulted on sensitive matters and strategies to address food-deprived and vulnerable groups and the inclusion of gender aspects.

Key things to remember:

- Choose images that do not reinforce gender stereotypes.
- Do not use ‘man’ or ‘he’ to refer to the experiences of all people.
- Opt for gender-neutral language (third person plural: “they”, “them”).
- Use neutral terms such as parent (instead of father and mother) and partner (instead of husband, wife, boyfriend, and girlfriend).

2.5 ABLEISM

Recognising and avoiding ableist language is crucial:

- Do not use derogatory terms for medical disorders.
- Do not use the names of real conditions, to describe other behaviours.
- When writing about disabilities, do not describe people by their diagnosis, e.g. use ‘has dyslexia’ instead of ‘is dyslexic’.
- Avoid victimisation, e.g. use ‘uses a wheelchair’ instead of ‘wheelchair bound’.
- Do not write about disabilities, if it is not relevant to the content.
- Use ‘people with disabilities’, instead of terms grouping people such as ‘the disabled’ or ‘the handicapped’, etc.
- ‘Non-disabled’ is an appropriate term to use when referring to a person that is not disabled, not terms such as ‘normal’, ‘able-bodied’.

2.6 TERMINOLOGY

The FoodCLIC partners will ensure that project outputs, e.g. deliverables, are tailored to the target audiences, ensuring they are understandable to audiences unfamiliar with the EU-project realm. Project specific terms and abbreviations should always be defined in any public dissemination and communication. Avoid jargon at all costs! FoodCLIC partners can check with the communication and dissemination lead (ICLEI ES) ahead of writing any public deliverable on how to shape it from a communications standpoint.

ICLEI ES notes the frequent use of the terms listed below in internal communication. Please be aware that most of these terms have evolved into "FoodCLIC terminology" that is not necessarily common sense for external stakeholders. Therefore, when using these terms, project team members should take care to explain them or use commonly known (easy-to-understand) terms instead - especially when addressing the broader public, consumers and representatives of other professional fields.

In order to standardise the use of certain terms within the project, the contents of the terminology list below were aligned with the glossary of Deliverable 2.2 during the development of the "First updated version of the communication and dissemination plan" (D5.7).

FoodCLIC terminology	(Background) information that can be given to explain technical terms (terms and clauses in brackets can be left out to simplify sentence structure):
Food Systems	<p>Food systems are very complex and characterised by entanglements of (sometimes invisible, hidden, unfair or exclusionary) relations between multiple stakeholders.²</p> <p>"Food systems are the combination of all actions it takes to produce and consume our food on a day-to-day basis - from farm to fork to landfill. Food systems include any activity that produces, aggregates, processes, distributes, consumes or disposes food."³</p> <p>Food systems "incorporate[] all elements and activities that relate to the production, processing, distribution, preparation and consumption of food, as well as its disposal. This includes the environment, people, processes, infrastructure, institutions and the effects of their activities on our society, economy, landscape and climate."⁴</p> <p><i>Please avoid referring to "the food system" and rather make it plural "the (city-region) food systems".</i></p>

² based on statement from Prof. Roberta Sonnino, University of Surrey

³ The World Bank: [Food Systems 2030](#)

⁴ European Commission, FOOD 2030 Independent Expert Group (2018): [Recipe for Change: An Agenda for a Climate-Smart and Sustainable Food System for a Healthy Europe](#)

Food Systems Transformation	Food systems transformation “is the process of fundamental change in the structural, functional and relational aspects of the <u>food system</u> that leads to more equitable relationships and more benign patterns of interactions and outcomes.” ⁵
Food Poverty	The inability to acquire or consume an adequate or sufficient quantity of food in socially acceptable ways, or the uncertainty that one will be able to do so.
Food Insecurity	“A person is food insecure when they lack regular access to enough safe and nutritious food for normal growth and development and an active and healthy life. This may be due to unavailability of food and/or lack of resources to obtain food. Food insecurity can be experienced at different levels of severity.” ⁶
Food Security	“[A]ll people, at all times, have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their food preferences and dietary needs for an active and healthy life.” ⁷
City-Region Food System	<p>In simple terms, a ‘city-region’ describes a geographical region with a concentrated urban centre and rural or agricultural areas that sit within the regional hinterland of a city (i.e. a city and its surrounding rural area). Consequently, the term ‘city-region food system’ refers to a complex network of actors, processes and relationships related to food production, processing, distribution and consumption within this geographical region.⁸</p> <p>FoodCLIC operates in eight city-regions: Barcelona (Spain), Lisbon (Portugal), Amsterdam (Netherlands), Aarhus (Denmark), Berlin (Germany), Budapest (Hungary), Brasov (Romania), and the Plain of Lucca (Italy). These city-regions share the ambition of promoting the food system transformation, by improving their urban food environments and the (interrelated) urban food systems (to ensure that inhabitants have access to affordable, healthy and sustainably sourced food).</p> <p>This approach includes the explicit perspectives of rural and urban dynamics and needs. The ‘city-region food system’-concept rests upon the idea that increasing (support for) food localization, i.e. a better interconnection and complementary development of urban and rural areas, which are surrounding a city, is critical to transitioning towards a sustainable food system that tackles current nutritional challenges.⁹</p> <p>In each of these city-regions a Food Policy Network will be founded and/ or strengthened in the course of the FoodCLIC project.</p> <p>Eight city-regions with a Food Policy Network, a public authority and a higher education and research institution, will form the backbone of FoodCLIC’s Living Labs, where real-life interventions will be designed and implemented for in-depth study, learning and knowledge-sharing within selected urban food environments.</p>

⁵ Prof. Roberta Sonnino, University of Surrey

⁶ FAO: [Hunger and Food Insecurity](#)

⁷ International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI): [Food Security](#)

⁸ Jennings, S. et al. (2015): Food in an urbanised world - The role of city-regions food systems in resilience and sustainable development. London: The Prince of Wales Charitable Foundation

⁹ based on Jennings, S. et al. (2015), see 8

	<p>A key assumption of FoodCLIC is that, (if properly supported by thoroughly integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks,) positive changes in the urban food environment can have equally positive repercussions for the wider city-region food system and vice versa.¹⁰</p>
<p>(urban, local) Food environment</p>	<p><i>The glossary¹¹ in the Grant Agreement lists the term “food environment” and more specified terms, such as “retail food environment”, “hospitality food environment”, “institutional food environment”, and “agri-food environment”.</i></p> <p><i>Wherever possible, please try to use more commonly known expressions, such as “food retail (sector)”, “hospitality sector” or simply “restaurants” etc. or try to be more precise by using the term “urban food environment”.</i></p> <p><i>In FoodCLIC, we are often referring to six specific neighbourhood food environments: agri-food (gardens), hospitality (takeaways), retail (supermarkets), community (food-consumer cooperative), institutional (school canteen), wild (berry bushes).</i></p>
<p>Food Policy, Food Policymaking</p> <p>and Integrated Food Policy</p>	<p>‘Food policy (-making)’ describes the area of public policy concerning how food is produced, processed, distributed, purchased and provided. Food policies are influencing the food system(s) and the agriculture system(s), ideally with a view to their influence on sustainability, the environment, human health and socio-economic aspects.</p> <p>By using policy instruments (e.g. laws and (tax) regulations, (urban) land-use planning, investments and subsidy schemes, communication strategies, covenants, etc.), food policies can affect the supply or prices of food products, their safety and nutritional composition, or the information consumers receive about food, which in turn influences the consumers’ food choice(s) and, ultimately, the nutritional quality of their diets, i.e. the human health.</p> <p>The goal of a food policy is to have a safe, wholesome, nutritious, culturally appropriate food (supply) that is economically accessible for everyone, and available in adequate amounts to promote health, prevent dietary deficiency, and reduce other diet-related diseases.</p> <p>FoodCLIC aims at creating a positive impact through the development of (integrated and evidence-based) food policies, i.e. policies, which build on state-of-the-art scientific knowledge and experiential knowledge and which deal with food production, processing, distribution and provision, taking into account a food system’s influence on sustainability, the environment, human health as well as socio-economic aspects.”</p> <p>Integrated food policies acknowledge the interdependencies between food concerns and other relevant policy domains, and “work along the four pillars of the project’s CLIC framework to (i) realize sustainability <u>C</u>o-benefits, (ii) establish <u>L</u>inkages between urban and rural areas, (iii) <u>I</u>nclude all relevant food system stakeholders, and (iv) build <u>C</u>onnections between food and other policy domains.”¹²</p> <p>“FoodCLIC’s development of integrated urban food policies builds upon evidence</p>

¹⁰ Grant Agreement, Annex 1, Part B, p. 15 (PDF-p. 126)

¹¹ Grant Agreement, Annex 1, Part B, p. 4 (PDF-p. 115)

¹² Grant Agreement, Annex 1, Part B, p. 4 (PDF-p. 115)

Food-related policies	<p>generated through real-life interventions.”¹³</p> <p><i>From Deliverable 2.2:</i> <i>“Policies that engage with food (i.e., policies that mention food) but not as the main focus. Instead, their main focus might be climate, health, etc.”</i></p>
Food Policy Network	<p>A ‘Food Policy Network’ is an organisational framework that represents multiple stakeholders and that is either sanctioned by a government body or exists independently of a government. A FPN facilitates interdisciplinary exchange and active involvement of multiple stakeholders, such as decision makers and interested parties from the fields of food sourcing, processing and supply, politicians/ policy actors and public planning representatives, with a specific focus on the inclusion of food-deprived and vulnerable communities, as well as of municipal, regional and national government authorities with the capacity to effect changes in the urban food environment and the wider food system of a city, county, state, tribal, multi-county or other designated region.</p> <p>Through the Food Policy Networks, FoodCLIC will work closely with the 45 cities and towns belonging to the eight city-regions.</p> <p>A Food Policy Network will be founded and/ or strengthened in each of FoodCLIC’s eight city-regions to formulate an integrated food strategy with the objective to have a safe, wholesome, nutritious, culturally appropriate food (supply) that is economically accessible for everyone. Combined with the learnings generated through real-life interventions, this strategy will provide the foundation for the development of evidence-based and integrated urban food policies as well as urban planning frameworks, which include food concerns and acknowledge the interdependencies between ‘food’ and other relevant policy domains.</p>
Food-sensitive planning frameworks	<p>“At the same time, it is critical that urban planners pay serious attention to the role of (urban) food environments and food concerns in their planning frameworks, given the connections between food and other public goods, such as human and environmental health, wellbeing and sustainability.”¹⁴ They need to become food-sensitive.</p> <p>Urban planning frameworks, i.e. strategies, processes and regulations concerning the physical, material or spatial development of an urban area, should always</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ... consider and include food priorities/ food concerns. They should be food-sensitive. • ... acknowledge the interdependencies between food concerns and other relevant policy domains and be aware of the role of food in urban planning. <p><i>In other words: Given that most cities have one planning framework that addresses all domains/ sectors in relation to spatial planning, FoodCLIC is not asking for a planning framework that specifically focuses on food, but for planning frameworks that include food concerns, i.e. that are food-sensitive.</i></p>

¹³ Grant Agreement, Annex 1, Part B, p. 18-19 (PDF-p. 129-130)

¹⁴ Grant Agreement, Annex 1, Part B, p. 5 (PDF-p. 116)

CLIC (framework)¹⁵

The CLIC is a (normative, innovative, methodological, conceptual) framework, which describes the desired process shape and outcomes of the food system transformation.^{16 17}

In practice the CLIC (framework) constitutes the foundation model of the FoodCLIC project, i.e. provides guidelines for all action taken within the scope of the FoodCLIC project, such as the analysis of good practices, the design and evaluation of real-life interventions in the selected urban food environments, the formulation of integrated urban food policies, and the development of urban planning frameworks.

The CLIC (framework) is built on 4 pillars, which can be seen as FoodCLIC's (4 tangible and interrelated) goals for food system transformation.

They are:

- The creation of co-benefits (/ synergies) between social, economic and environmental objectives (of sustainability).
 - Urban agriculture, as an example, creates social cohesion and employment opportunities, reconnects people with nature and increases access to (locally produced) fruit and vegetables.
 - This aspect builds on the understanding that action dedicated to promoting sustainability in a certain sector may impact other parts of a system in a positive (synergy, co-benefit) OR negative (trade-off) way.
- The establishment of (sustainable) linkages between urban and rural areas, and between land and water.
 - In practice this means that focus should lie on food distribution channels (such as wholesale or farmers markets) that enhance the availability, accessibility and affordability of healthy and nutritious food for all.
- The inclusion of all food stakeholders (including food producers, processors, packagers, retailers, distributors, storage and waste managers, and consumers from different socio-economic groups) and their knowledge, which translates to 'active and meaningful involvement of all actors in the food system transformation (and in the design and implementation of food policies), including food-deprived and vulnerable groups'.
- Awareness raising for existing connectivities between food and other policy priorities/ systems/ sectors (e.g. health, welfare, housing, transport/ mobility/ energy), as these interactions entail the need for holistic solutions.
 - This means that, for example, food insecurity or food poverty should not be seen as an alone-standing phenomenon. Instead, food insecurities are indicative of underlying socio-economic and environmental problems that require to be addressed holistically.
 - "In urban planning, for example, the allocation of space for food production, distribution and consumption often overlaps and competes with other possible land-uses (including, but not limited to, housing, schools and green infrastructure). Under the guidance of the CLIC framework, FoodCLIC will explicitly seek to build on the interactions between food and other systems and investigate how

¹⁵ based on Prof. Roberta Sonnino, University of Surrey

¹⁶ The CLIC concept has been derived from the work of Sonnino et al. (2016) on place-based approach in food system transformation (see 17)

¹⁷ Sonnino, R. et al (2016): Relationalities and convergences in food security narratives: towards a place-based approach. Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers, 41(4), pp.477-489.

	<p>these can be made productive, in terms of creating win-win situations”¹⁸, e.g. through mixed-use concepts in urban planning.</p> <p>As such, the CLIC (framework) ...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • promotes system thinking. • highlights the relevance of “place” as a relational, multi-scalar and socially produced entity. • recognizes the multi-dimensionality of food system transformation. • guides the design of integrated urban food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks. • guides all food system actors through the process of food system transformation, building on a broadened and deepened meaning of “integration” being reflected in its 4 pillars/ key dimensions. <p>The CLIC has been derived from the work of Sonnino et al. (2016) on place-based approach in food system transformation.</p>
<p>Living Lab</p>	<p>Living Labs are virtual and physical spaces, where (members of the city-regions and Food Policy Networks, i.e.) research organizations, inhabitants, companies, public authorities and other stakeholders come together</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ... to learn and experiment through so-called real-life interventions. • ... to understand the food system, to design, implement, test, analyse and evaluate research and innovation processes in the form of so-called real-life interventions in real-life communities and settings with the aim to produce learnings and knowledge and to prepare for up-scaling innovation, and with the wider goal of building a policy-relevant evidence-base through learning-in-action.
<p>Science-policy-practice interface</p>	<p>Through capacity-building, the learnings and knowledge generated through real-life interventions in its Living Labs, and the close collaboration and relationship building in the Food Policy Networks, FoodCLIC targets the establishment and promotion of strong science-policy-practice interfaces. This is to foster continuous, inclusive, and productive exchanges between urban food policy-makers, urban planners and a wide range of stakeholders, who will be producing, learning, and reflecting on the evidence-base for the development of integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks (= urban planning that takes into account that ‘food’ interrelates with other (policy) fields, such as health and environment).</p>
<p>(Public) (Food) Procurement</p>	<p>‘(Public) (Food) procurement’ is a technical term and its meaning may not be clear to all of FoodCLIC’s stakeholders (e.g. the general public). Therefore, when using it in certain contexts or situations, please explain the meaning of this term.</p> <p>‘Public procurement’ refers to the purchase by governments or public authorities of specified goods, services and works from external parties.¹⁹</p> <p>The term ‘public food procurement’ describes the process of specifying, buying and providing food to publicly administered spaces, such as canteens. ^{20 21}</p>

¹⁸ Grant Agreement, Annex 1, Part B, p. 10 (PDF-p. 121)

¹⁹ OECD, [Public procurement](#)

²⁰ FoodCorps, [From the Source: School Food Procurement 101](#)

²¹ Slow Food: [How can sustainable food procurement help reshaping food systems?](#)

Food-deprived and vulnerable groups

In simple terms, the procurement process (or purchasing process) includes (amongst other things) collecting information, inquiries, price comparisons, negotiations, decisions, orderings, coordination and communication and payment.

Public procurement takes place within a framework consisting of defined laws, regulations and procedures that guide government purchases.²² Depending on these policy and regulatory frameworks, public (food) procurement (initiatives) can have an influence on:

- what kind of food will be purchased (e.g. local, nutritious, healthy, plant based...)
- from whom it will be purchased (e.g. from local or smallholder farmers, small and medium food enterprises, or women, youth or other vulnerable producers)
- From what type of production it will be purchased (e.g. from organic agriculture)

“Considering the extent of the demand for food from the public sector, public food procurement has the potential to profoundly influence different components of food systems (such as consumption and production patterns). It affects a wide range of actors and has the potential to deliver multiple social, economic and/ or environmental benefits to multiple beneficiaries, including producers and consumers and the wider community.”²³

The European Commission's Farm to Fork Strategy plans the definition of “minimum mandatory criteria for sustainable food procurement to promote healthy and sustainable diets, including organic products, in schools and public institutions.”²⁴

People whose diets are lacking in caloric quantity or nutritional quality (resulting in food safety risks and undernutrition) on account of limited access as a result of local availability, living on low income and/or personal circumstances (e.g. institutionalised persons).²⁵

FoodCLIC aims at the inclusion of all food system actors and people, while ensuring a fair(er) distribution of its project outcomes.

Wherever possible, please use the terms “vulnerable groups/ communities/ people” or “food-deprived groups/ communities/ people”, when referring to a group of people with fewer resources. You can also say “people facing systemic barriers”, “people living in food deserts” or “people whose diets are lacking in quantity or nutritional quality due to limited access as a result of spatiality, living on low income and/ or personal circumstances”.

When referring to a geographical area, we recommend to use the terms “deprived food regions/ neighbourhoods/ areas (within a city-region)”.

²² Based on FAO (2018): [Strengthening sector policies for better food security and nutrition results](#)

²³ FAO, Alliance of Bioversity International and CIAT and Editora da UFRGS (2021): [Public food procurement for sustainable food systems and healthy diets](#), Volume 1

²⁴ European Commission, Food Safety, [Sustainable food consumption](#)

²⁵ Grant Agreement, Annex 1, Part B, p. 4 (PDF-p. 115)

**Community
Supported
Agriculture
(CSA)**

From Deliverable 2.2:

CSA "means a direct partnership between one or more farmers and the consumers. The latter help to guarantee all or part of the agricultural activity budget, through a pre-financing. They pay in advance their share of the harvest that will take place in the following year, sharing risks and benefits."

2.7 LOCAL LANGUAGES AND TRANSLATION

The FoodCLIC city-regions, with its Living Labs, are located in eight different countries and each aim to involve a broad range of stakeholders with different backgrounds (e.g. research organisations, inhabitants, companies, public authorities). It is anticipated that communication and dialogue with and between these stakeholders on-site will take place in the respective local language, led by the city-regions with materials provided in English by ICLEI ES. Within the project consortium, all city-region research partners have allocated budget for translation.

Whenever possible, ICLEI ES provides project partners with easy-to-edit templates in English that can be translated by the project partners. For the purpose of knowledge sharing, project partners are continuously invited to share locally produced materials with the entire consortium.

2.8 KEY MESSAGES

BASELINE

Socio-economic, environmental, and health-related issues converge within the urban food environment.

But: At present, urban food environments do not ensure that the healthy and sustainable option is always “the easiest one”.

... with a focus on social/ socio-economic aspects:

An increasing number of people face difficulties in accessing and affording healthy, safe and sustainably produced food.

People with fewer resources are often steered towards unhealthy, highly processed and packaged food, delivered by unsustainable food systems, which are characterised by carbon-intensive production methods that use of artificial fertilisers and pesticides, and contribute to soil and water degradation and often disregard animal welfare issues.

Consumption practices are shaped by decisions on purchasing, preparing and consuming food, which in turn are influenced by the availability, affordability and attractiveness of different kinds of foods.

Rationale:

Urbanization: While nowadays approximately 55% of the global population live in **urban areas**, this share is expected to increase to 68 % by 2050.²⁶

Climate Change: Climate change, which is hampering food production through increasing temperatures, changing precipitation patterns and more frequent natural disasters, is already affecting and will increasingly affect food security.²⁷

Russia's invasion to Ukraine: Russia's war against Ukraine and its use of food as a weapon of war have strongly impacted food markets, as Russia's military aggression has caused both: scarcity of food and high increases in food and fertiliser prices.

High food prices: Inflation and "high food prices affect people's ability to access basic (let alone sustainable and healthy) food", resulting in rising levels of food poverty and adding "further pressure on low-income households" as well as vulnerable groups, "which are affected most".²⁸

Increased food prices resulting from disruptions in production and transport directly impact consumers, especially the most vulnerable groups in city regions that are highly dependent on affordable food.²⁹

Insufficient income (and inadequate minimum income policies) is a driver of food insecurity and a key barrier to access a healthy diet in Europe. In 16 out of 24 countries at least 10% of the population in (sub) urban areas risks to be confronted with income-related food insecurity. Policies directed at tackling food insecurity should be embedded in broader economic and social policies.

²⁶ FAO (2022): [City Region Food Systems Programme – Reinforcing rural-urban linkages for resilient food systems](#)

²⁷ IPCC: [Special Report on Climate Change and Land](#)

²⁸ Council of the European Union (2022): [Food security and affordability](#)

²⁹ FAO (2022): [City Region Food Systems Programme – Reinforcing rural-urban linkages for resilient food systems](#)

	<p>In rich welfare states the problem of food insecurity is not so much an issue of undernourishment, but rather of lacking access to a healthy diet.³⁰</p> <p><u>Supporting statistics:</u> Harmonized index of consumer prices (HICP) inflation rate for food and non-alcoholic beverages in the EU³¹ Inflation rate for food in the European Union (EU) from May 2015 to June 2022³²</p>
<p>People who can afford to purchase sustainable and healthy food often lack meaningful reasons and motivation to do so, or face a lack of choices.</p>	<p>Studies examining Chile's innovative food regulation act, compiling three essential measures (clear labels on packaging to highlight unhealthy ingredients; restricted sales of certain food products in schools and its surrounding areas; and limited advertising of certain food products to children), show that the measures rolled out to limit unhealthy consumption, have positively influenced nutritional preferences and consumer behaviour and have the potential to change food norms.³³</p> <p>There is an appetite for change from EU consumers. Three out of five Europeans want to eat more sustainably and three out of four want EU legislation to ensure that all products sold in the EU do not lead to biodiversity loss.³⁴</p>

<p>... with a focus on health:</p> <p>Vulnerable people, such as the elderly or those in long-term hospital care, or in care homes are often at risk of malnutrition in the European Union.</p>	<p>Rationale:</p> <p>Older people are often unable to meet their nutritional needs through their normal diet and are, therefore, more at risk of malnutrition. Malnutrition is caused by inadequate intake of energy, protein and/or other nutrients as a result of diseases or their treatment or loss of appetite. Despite the availability of screening tools, malnutrition among older people often goes undetected and untreated.³⁵</p>
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³⁰ Tess Penne, Tim Goedemé (2021): Can low-income households afford a healthy diet? Insufficient income as a driver of food insecurity in Europe, Food Policy, Volume 99

³¹ Statista (2022): [Harmonized index of consumer prices \(HICP\) inflation rate for food and non-alcoholic beverages in the European Union from January 1997 to November 2022](#)

³² Statista (2022): [Inflation rate for food in the European Union \(EU\) from January 2016 to October 2022](#)

³³ World Economic Forum (2020): [Incentivizing Food Systems Transformation](#)

³⁴ [WWF \(2022\): Report - Europe eats the World](#)

³⁵ Medical Nutrition Industry (2020): MNI contribution to the European Commission's Roadmap "Demographic change in Europe - green paper on ageing

The number of overweight or obese European citizens is rising, causing an increasing number of diet-related health problems (diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and certain cancers).

In the European Region, 59% of adults and almost 1 in 3 children are overweight or living with obesity. Obesity has been identified as a serious public health challenge at both individual and population levels, as it increases the risk for many diseases, including cancers, cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes mellitus and chronic respiratory diseases.³⁶

... with a focus on food production/ supply:

Small-scale farmers, fishers and workers involved in harvesting and processing are struggling to earn a living wage.

Rationale:

"[T]he average farm income in the EU [reached] €35,300 per farm and €22,500 per annual working unit in 2018. However, significant differences can be observed across the EU and based on types of farming, sex, age and level of training of farm holders and managers."³⁷

"The main reason for low farm incomes is the low market price of agricultural products. Real prices [agricultural products] have been declining since [years and] productivity growth has not kept up with the decline. [...]

Since the average age of farmers in the European Union is between 50 and 60 and increasing, the rate of farm abandonment may dramatically increase through 2030. [...] Since an income of ~20k is not an appealing prospect, it is no surprise that young farmers are few in number. Moreover, farm income is around 40% lower than non-agricultural income. Lastly, the farm income has been mostly flat in the past decade despite a decrease in the number of farmers and an increase in average farm size. [...]

The EU Farm Economics Overview³⁸ found that the average hourly wage of farm workers was €7.90 in the EU-28 in 2015. Eurostat reported €23.1 as the EU's average hourly wage in 2017. Farm worker wages are close to the minimum wages in most EU countries. In Greece and Slovenia, farm workers earned less than minimum wage in 2018."³⁹

³⁶ WHO (2022): [European Regional Obesity Report](#)

³⁷ European Commission (2021): [Farm income increased over last decade, with important differences between EU countries](#)

³⁸ European Commission – DG for Agriculture and Rural Development (2021): [EU Farm Economics Overview FADN 2018](#)

³⁹ Farm Europe (2021): [EU rural incomes and biofuels](#)

Unsustainable food systems create fragile supply chains that are particularly susceptible to sudden shocks (e.g. a pandemic).

"A company's entire supply chain can make a significant impact in promoting human rights, fair labour practices, environmental progress and anti-corruption policies."⁴⁰

"The COVID-19 crisis, post pandemic economic effects, and the ongoing conflict in Ukraine have exposed the vulnerabilities of today's global supply chains. [...] Supply chain leaders now find themselves in an unfamiliar position: they have the attention of top management and a mandate to make real change. [...] They can do that by recognizing the three new priorities alongside the function's traditional objectives of cost/capital, quality, and service and redesigning their supply chains accordingly:" resilience, agility and sustainability.⁴¹

... with a focus on the food and climate change nexus:

Current dietary patterns and the wider organisation of food systems are responsible for significant environmental challenges (soil degradation, monoculture, forest clearances/ deforestation, GHG emissions ...).

Food systems contribute significantly to climate change: agriculture alone is responsible for 10 % of the European Union's greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and food practices contribute to 17% of these emissions, which is expected to increase considerably if dietary patterns do not change.

Rationale:

Food systems account for more than one third of global greenhouse gas emissions (i.e. 34 %). Current food systems produce around 30 percent of global greenhouse gases. Thus, changing food habits and transforming current food systems is a central solution to addressing the climate crises.⁴²

Human destruction of nature has caused a 69% drop in species population size since 1970. Food systems are a primary driver of biodiversity loss through unsustainable food production methods and habitat loss.⁴³

⁴⁰ United Nations Global Compact: [Apply sustainable practices throughout the supply chain](#)

⁴¹ McKinsey & Company (2022): [Future-proofing the supply chain](#)

⁴² FAO (2021): [Food systems account for more than one third of global greenhouse gas emissions](#)

⁴³ WWF (2022): [Living Planet Report 2022](#)

... with a focus on food waste:

One fifth of food produced is wasted. This amplifies the negative impact of dietary patterns and food systems/ production and supply chains on the environment.

Overconsumption and food waste puts unnecessary pressure on the environment.

Rational

Globally, about one third of all food produced is wasted.⁴⁴

If food waste was considered a country, it would come third after USA and China in terms of GHG emissions.⁴⁵

In 2020, the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic, around 127 kilogrammes (kg) of food per inhabitant were wasted in the EU.⁴⁶

Messages to policy makers, local governments/ municipalities and urban planners:

There are many (food) innovations and successful pilots to transform our food systems. To scale these up, policy support is needed.

Food needs to be included as a consideration in urban policy-making to ensure healthy and happy people.

Urban planning needs to incorporate food considerations in planning processes (across land, housing, air quality and physical infrastructure) due to the interconnectedness of food concerns with other relevant sectors.

Urban planners need to become 'food sensitive', giving consideration to the food environment, as food is inherently tied to other public goods, and human and environmental health, wellbeing and sustainability.

Integrated food policies can help meet other targets related to areas such as climate, health, biodiversity, and green space.

Food policies need to be bridged with planning systems, such as land-use plans and zoning laws, to ensure good production, processing, distribution and consumption of affordable, healthy and sustainable food.

Growing, sourcing and preparing the ingredients for (school) food in a sustainable way, is important for municipalities and countries to achieve the targets of the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the Paris Agreement on climate change. Your contribution is indispensable!

⁴⁴ FAO (2011): [Global food losses and food waste – extent, causes and prevention](#)

⁴⁵ World Food Programme (2020): [5 facts about food waste and hunger](#)

⁴⁶ Eurostat (2022): [Food waste: 127 kg per inhabitant in the EU in 2020](#)

**Promotional:
FoodCLIC**

– integrated urban food policies to transform food systems in city-regions

At present, urban food environments do not ensure that healthy and sustainable food is the easy, affordable and available option for all.

FoodCLIC is here to transform this.

Creating integrated food and planning frameworks in cities and towns can be challenging. **FoodCLIC aims at integrating all four Food2030 priorities** (health, climate, circularity and inclusion) at the same time.

FoodCLIC actively supports people’s access to affordable healthy and sustainable food

- ... by creating resilient and inclusive urban food networks.
- ... by improving food policies & planning frameworks through the CLIC framework.
- ... by creating connectivities between food and other systems / policies.
- ... by creating learning experiences through practical work in eight Food Policy Networks/ city-regions, (encompassing 45 cities and towns): metropolitan area of Barcelona, Berlin region, Aarhus region, metropolitan region Amsterdam, Lisbon metropolitan area, Budapest region, Brasov metropolitan area and Plain of Lucca.
- ... by easing access to affordable, healthy and sustainable food.

To bring about real change, we can’t work in silos and with one challenge at a time.

We need to co-create our new school food system together.

FoodCLIC aims for healthy and sustainable food to be the easy, affordable and available option at local level.

FoodCLIC helps municipalities implement integrated food and planning frameworks.

FoodCLIC empowers people.

FoodCLIC supports policy makers.

FoodCLIC promotes the implementation of integrated planning frameworks.

A the heart of FoodCLIC is an innovative conceptual framework (the CLIC), based on system thinking, which will guide all food system actors towards **four desired outcomes of integration**:

- sustainability Co-benefits;
- strengthened rural-urban Linkages across the food system;
- the Inclusion of all food stakeholders; and
- the creation of new Connectivities between food and other complex systems and policy priorities);

I.e. the CLIC is a concept that is simultaneously social, spatial, environmental and political.

FoodCLIC applies system thinking to simultaneously establish social, spatial, environmental and political integration.

FoodCLIC works on **'science-policy-practice' interfaces** (SPPIs) to develop integrated food policies, food sensitive planning frameworks and to foster meaningful exchanges between urban food policy-makers, planners, designers and a wide range of stakeholders across local food environments. SPPIs enable to approach the facilitators and barriers of urban food systems, and the transformation needed to enable upscaling of urban food policy pilots.

FoodCLIC establishes interfaces and relationships between food science, policy and practice areas.

FoodCLIC will create inclusive and resilient urban food environments.

FoodCLIC creates inclusive and resilient urban food environments.

Specific advocacy messages can be found in the ['Advocacy plan for interaction with higher level authorities'](#) (D4.1).

3. TARGET AUDIENCES

FoodCLIC target audiences are those who need, advocate or work with, or have the opportunity to influence access to affordable, attractive, sustainable and healthy food.

Figure 3: FoodCLIC target audiences

Direct stakeholders are those involved in the Food Policy networks and in the eight partner and eight extension city regions (Living Labs):

- Food-deprived and vulnerable groups
 - school children
 - elderly in care homes
 - patients in hospitals
- Inhabitants and consumers
- HEIs and ROs
- CSOs, including NGOs
- Policy-makers (local and regional)
- Urban planners
- Public procurement officers
- Foodbanks and charities
- Food-related businesses:
 - farmers, fishers
 - retail, restaurants
 - markets, distribution centres
 - processing and storage
 - logistics

Adopters of strategies are the stakeholders not directly involved in the 8+8 FoodCLIC city regions. They contain the same actors as the above listing and stakeholders reached through the high-level Think Tank and project partners' networks: ICLEI (~160 municipalities in Europe and 2,500 globally), Metropolis (140+ metropolises globally), European Metropolitan Authorities (50 members) and FEBA (~430 food banks).

National, European and international stakeholders, such as media, health care networks and health insurance companies, as well as associations and platforms working on food at different levels are a third audience group. They include networks (including MUFFP, RUAF and FOOD2030), EU Green Deal and HE projects (e.g. FOODSHIFT2030, FUSILLI and FOODTRAILS), National, European and international food policymakers (including the high-level Think Tank), Media, Health care and health insurance companies, Associations and platforms working on food at different levels

<p>Communication will promote the project's activities mainly to non-specialist audiences, including the media and the general public, with the goal of increasing awareness about, and understanding of, FoodCLIC's objectives.</p>	<p>Dissemination will target a more technical audience, including researchers, SMEs, specialised practitioners (e.g., food bank staff, managers of urban gardens, urban planners, etc.) and potential adopters and replicators, including policymakers and FPNs, with the aim of sharing the project's findings and outcomes with potential users.</p>
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A stakeholder database will be built based on inputs from WP2-3 and inputs of all partners throughout the project that will include relevant entities to disseminate and communicate to in each target audience category. It will include a list of innovative SMEs, social innovators, planners and urban designers, particularly young professionals who could be interested in adopting the innovative, inclusive and sustainable business models (based on synergies between public health, the environment, the economy and social welfare) that FoodCLIC aims to develop.

4. TOOLS AND CHANNELS

The project communication and dissemination will take place via various means, from both project and partner channels. The below chapter lists the project channels, tools and multipliers. Partner channels have been gathered by ICLEI ES through the 'Survey for partners' communication and dissemination channels' issued in M2.

4.1 CHANNELS

4.1.1 WEBSITE

The project website was created during the first six months of the project: <https://foodclic.eu/> . The FoodCLIC website contains general project information ([ABOUT](#)), presents the eight Pilot city-regions (e.g. [AARHUS](#)) as well as project outcomes and news ([BLOG](#)), provides contact information ([CONTACT](#)), promotes the Broadening Call for Participation ([APPLY NOW!](#)), and lists resources ([KNOWLEDGE HUB](#), to be added in March 2024).

The website now also presents all members of the [Think Tank](#) and the [Stakeholder Advisory Board](#).

A detailed overview of the established website structure and its content was presented in Deliverable 5.3 (March 2023).

In the future, it is planned that the website incorporates or links to the FPN Platform (WP4).

The website will be kept online (unmaintained) for some years after the end of the project. The partner websites will be used for wider dissemination of key products and to raise awareness about the project. The news sections of partner websites (if available) will be utilised to share FoodCLIC updates. The databases and resource sites indicated can be used to include and upload findings. Further the EIP-AGRI (The agricultural European Innovation Partnership) website will be used for broad dissemination to practitioners.

International organisations	Non-Governmental foundations	Research institutes/ organisations	Municipalities
ICLEI Europe News section Resources	CARIPLO News section	UNIVERSITA DI PISA News section	MUNICIPIUL BRASOV News section
World Association of the Major Metropolises (Metropolis) News section	FUNDACIO PRIVADA INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE LA SIDA-CAIXA News section	AARHUS UNIVERSITET	COMUNE DI CAPANNORI News section
ICLEI News section Resources	FONDAZIONE CENTRO EURO-MEDITERRANEOSUI CAMBIAMENTI CLIMATICI News section	STICHTING VU News Section Database	AARHUS KOMMUNE News section Database
	EUROPEAN FOOD BANKS FEDERATION (FEBA)	INSTITUTO DE CIENCIAS SOCIAIS	AREA METROPOLITANA DE BARCELONA News section 1 – 2

	Database		
	<u>ERNAHRUNGSRAT BERLIN E.V. News section</u>	<u>University of Surrey (AP) News section</u>	<u>BUDAPEST FOVAROS ONKORMANYZATA News section</u>
	<u>STICHTING VOEDSEL VERBINDT News section</u>	<u>HUMBOLDT- UNIVERSITAET ZU BERLIN Agricultural dept. News section</u>	<u>EMAC – CASCAIS AMBIENTE News section</u>
		<u>FACULDADE DE MEDICINA DA UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA News section</u>	
		<u>ESSRG NONPROFIT KFT</u>	

KPI: Project website (48+ blogs, 100+ project outputs; audience 1,000,000+)

4.1.2 SOCIAL MEDIA

LinkedIn:

FoodCLIC's first social media presence was launched on LinkedIn at the beginning of 2024. The profile can be accessed via the following link: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/foodcllic/>. With the launch of the FoodCLIC presence on LinkedIn, all project partners are encouraged to integrate FoodCLIC into their communication on LinkedIn.

Project partners are invited to tag the FoodCLIC profile whenever they mention the project:
@FoodCLIC

The following **topic-specific, relevant Hashtags** will be used when posting on LinkedIn. Project partners are invited to use these hashtags in their communication in connection with FoodCLIC: #FoodCLIC, #FoodSystems, #FoodEnvironments, #HealthyFood, #UrbanFood, #EUFOOD2030, #FarmToFork and #HorizonEU.

Project partners' LinkedIn profiles:	
PAGE - Pisa Agricultural Economics	ESSRG
University of Surrey	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin
Department of Food Science, AU FOOD	City of Aarhus
European Food Banks Federation - FEBA	Athena - Research and Education Institute
Ernährungsrat Berlin	Stichting Voedsel Verbindt
Cariplo Factory	IrsiCaixa AIDS Research Institute
Metropolis, World Association of the major metropolises	CMCC Foundation - Centro Euro Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici
Àrea Metropolitana de Barcelona (AMB)	ICLEI, ICLEI Europe
ICS - Instituto de Ciências Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa	Instituto de Saúde Ambiental (ISAMB)
Câmara Municipal de Cascais	Cascais Ambiente EMAC

Other projects' and network LinkedIn profiles:	
FOOD 2030 Networks	VISIONARY Project EU
TRUSTyFOOD	SWITCH
Project RURALITIES	FUSILLI Project
Foster Food System	FoodSHIFT 2030
SciFoodHealth	FOODCoST
Food Trails	FEAST
FAIRCHAIN_EU	ENFASYS HEU
The Edible Cities Network	COREnet
CULTIVATE	Buy Better Food

LinkedIn profiles related to EU institutions:	
EU Environment and Climate	European Committee of the Regions
European Research Executive Agency (REA)	EU Health and Food Safety

Other channels:

The addition of further profiles on other social media channels is being considered for the future. The channel's use will be adjusted to popular developments in the social media realm, and if a channel becomes disreputable then its use will be discontinued.

Partner Twitter channels (reach in January 2023): [@ICLEI_Europe](#) (21k+), [ICLEI](#) (41k+), [@Metropolis_org](#) (25k+), [@PagePisa](#) (900+), [@essrg](#) (260+), [@UniOfSurrey](#) (64k+), [@ComuneCapannori](#) (2k+), [@AarhusUni_int](#) (3k+) - [@AarhusUni](#) (22k+) - [@AUSenseDK](#) (500+), [@EuroFoodBanks](#) (900+), [@VUamsterdam](#) (56k+) - [@AthenaInst](#) (600+), [@Ernaehrungsrat](#) (800+), [@VOEDSELVERBINDT](#) (300+), [@CariploFactory](#) (2k+), [@IrsiCaixa](#) (7k+), [@EMAMetropolitan](#) (300+) - [@PremsaAMB](#) (2k+) - [@SocioEconAMB](#) (1k+) - [@AgenciaEconAMB](#) (1k+) - [@sostAMB](#) (8k+) - [@ParcsplatgesAMB](#) (1k+) - [@JugatecaAMB](#) (600+), [@CmccClimate](#) (6k+), [@icsunivlisboa](#) (3k+), [@AFP_HU](#) (700+), [@isamb_fmul](#) (160+), [@CMCascais](#) (4k+)

Partner Youtube channels: [@icleieurope](#), [@PrimariaMunicipiuluiBrasov](#), [@essrg9418](#), [@universityofsurrey](#), [@ComuneCapannori](#), [@metropolis_org](#), [@aakvideosite](#), [@EuropeanFoodBanksFederation](#), [@CanalCascais](#)

Partner Instagram channels: [eurofoodbanks](#), [uniofsurrey](#), [primaria_municipiului_brasov](#), [ernaehrungsratberlin](#), [voedselverbindt](#), [irsicaixa](#), [amb_metropolis](#), [cmccclimate](#), [cascais_oficial](#)

Partner Facebook channels: [European Food Banks Federation - FEBA](#), [Aarhus Kommune](#), [Metropolis - World Association of the Major Metropolises](#), [Piana del Cibo](#), [University of Surrey](#), [Primăria Municipiului Braşov](#), [Athena - Research and Education Institute](#), [Ernährungsrat Berlin](#), [Voedsel Verbindt](#), [Cariplo Factory](#), [AMB Metròpolis Barcelona](#), [Budapest Városháza](#), [CMCC Climate](#), [ICLEI World Secretariat](#), [ICS - Instituto de Ciências Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa](#), [Câmara Municipal de Cascais](#), [Ambiente Cascais](#)

Partner Blogs: [ICLEI City Talk](#), [Alimentacio metropolitana](#)

Partner Podcasts: [Local Voices for Sustainability](#)

KPI: FoodCLIC social media accounts (200+ posts on LinkedIn, Twitter/Mastodon, Youtube); audience 80,000+

4.1.3 MEDIA

ICLEI Europe's media partners will be utilised for targeted dissemination and communication about the project findings and products. Partners who indicated media contacts (scoped through 'Survey for partners' communication and dissemination channels') with media connections will be prompted to engage with their contacts, especially in the case of the municipalities and local associations involved, to ensure content is also shared in local languages. Press releases will be developed around major newsworthy (of interest to journalists) developments, events and advocacy days.

KPI: 10+ articles and press releases

4.1.4 NEWSLETTERS

ICLEI and Metropolis European and global mailing lists (37K+ subscribers) will be used to disseminate project results. Further the partners' newsletters where possible will share FoodCLIC updates. Those partners who indicated newsletters have an aggregate distribution of 129,000+.

KPI: 6 FoodCLIC e-newsletters, audience 1,500+

KPI: 50+ messages on ICLEI's and Metropolis' mailing lists; audience 37,000+

4.1.5 EVENTS

Figure 4: FoodCLIC events

FoodCLIC will engage with direct stakeholders through a series of training events. To reach the other stakeholders, a midterm and final high-level conference will be held alongside presentations and sessions in suitable national, European and international events (e.g. European Urban Resilience Forum, European Conference on Sustainable Cities and Towns, EU Week of Regions and Cities, EU Green Week, Food Poverty Symposium, Food policy council Year 2023, The Future of Food Conference, Farm to Fork Conference, European Food Forum Events, Sustainable Foods Summit).

Specifically, through WP4 (T4.2 ICLEI ES), a series of side events that will target public authorities at higher levels of governance will be organised (during European FOOD2030 High Level Events, European R&I Days, MUFPP Annual Gatherings, World Food Days, etc.). A short report to communicate the main outcomes of the mid-term and final conference will be published on the project's website to share the insights to all audiences. The training programme is aimed to increase the capacity of a broad range of stakeholders (including businesses, policy makers, researchers, SMEs, young professionals, public sector and CSOs) to enhance access to sustainable healthy food and to develop integrated urban food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks. The table shows the timing of FoodCLIC main and training events, and they are listed according to each work package below.

FoodCLIC events per Work Package:

WP4

1st FPN platform development workshop held / CARIPOLO / postponed to M16 (Dec. 2023) / Ms 13
2nd FPNs platform development workshop / CARIPOLO / postponed to M28 / Ms 23
1st HEI network meeting / VU / M26 / Ms 26
3rd FPN platform development workshop / CARIPOLO / postponed to M45 / Ms 31
2nd HEI network meeting / VU / M44 / Ms35
City-region national multi-stakeholder validation and discussion workshop on Living Lab results / HUB / M48 / Ms 36

WP3

City-region multi-stakeholder workshop on system analysis and visioning / HUB / postponed to M14 / Ms 14
City-region multi-stakeholder workshop on strategic planning / HUB / postponed to M17 / Ms17
City-region kick-off event on adaptive gov. + integrated policy making / VU / postponed to M25 / Ms 19
City-region multi-stakeholder co-design workshop real-life interventions / HUB / postponed to M19 / Ms 20
City-region 1st multi-stakeholder reflexive learning session / HUB / postponed to M26 / Ms 25
City-region 2nd multi-stakeholder reflexive learning session / HUB / postponed to M31 / Ms 29
City-region 3rd multi-stakeholder reflexive learning sessions / HUB / postponed to M37 / Ms 30
City-region 4th multi-stakeholder reflexive learning sessions / HUB / M42 / Ms 34

WP1

4th training of Living Lab teams on pathway selection and co-design / VU / postponed to M15 / Ms 15
5th training of Living Lab teams on implementation process through action learning cycles, including training on monitoring held / VU / postponed to M18 / Ms 18
Training of 1st cohort Living Labs to become peer trainers for 2nd cohort / VU / M22 / Ms 24

WP5

Mid-term international workshop / ICLEI ES / M26
Two workshops in Sub-Saharan Africa and South America / METROPOLIS / M49
Final international conference / ICLEI ES / M53

KPI: Presentations 15+ at international conferences - Audience 750+ (50 per event); 80+ at events in the partner city-regions, audience 10,000+;
1 mid-term and 1 final high-level conference

4.1.6 CLUSTERING & MULTIPLIERS

Where possible, FoodCLIC will bridge connections with other ongoing relevant EU-funded projects and other initiatives, and their communication and dissemination channels. Initial scoping of relevant initiatives was done through the 'Survey for partners' communication and dissemination channels' (connections in brackets):

- [CityFood](#) (ICLEI)
- [ZeroW](#), [SCHOOLFOOD4CHANGE](#), [Buy Better Food](#), [CHORIZO](#), [FEAST](#), [FOODPaths](#), [COACH](#), [SALSIFI](#) (ICLEI Europe)
- [SHERPA](#) (Universita di Pisa)
- [FOODSHIFT 2030](#), [FOOD WAVE](#) (Not directly implemented by Brasov Municipality, but by partners from the Metropolitan Agency of Brasov City)
- [TITAN](#) (University of Surrey)
- [Circular.rur](#), eLabHauSE (website upcoming), [Piana del Cibo](#) (Commune di Capannori)
- [InformPack](#) (Aarhus Universitet)
- [Circle U.](#) (Aarhus Kommune)
- [FUSILLI](#), [Soy Stories](#), [FOSTER](#), CLEVERFOOD, [TRUSTyFOOD](#), DOMINO, NATURELAB, [Supreme Nudge](#), [VeenVitaal](#), [Cropmix](#), [Duinboeren](#), [Cities 2030](#) (STICHTING VU), [FOODCITYBOOST](#) (STICHTING VU)
- [Foodshift 2030](#), [LebensMittelPunkte](#) (Ernährungsrat Berlin)
- Data Value Center Agri & Food short chain (Voedsel Verbindt)
- [Food Trails](#) (CARIPLO)
- [FOSTER](#), CLEVERFOOD (no website yet), and [Barcelona CaixaResearch Living Lab](#) (FUNDACIO PRIVADA INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE LA SIDA-CAIXA)
- [EARTHLY CITIES](#) (AREA METROPOLITANA DE BARCELONA)
- [SCHOOLFOOD4CHANGE](#), DIVINFOOD (BUDAPEST FOVAROS ONKORMANYZATA)

Further partners' close cooperation with a range of high-profile networks (including FOOD2030, the MUFPP, RUAF, etc.) will be utilised for dissemination. The [high-level Think Tank](#) (T5.1), which consists of 8-10 key experts from leading organisations in the field is a key multiplier to the participating organisations and the connected food related communities and initiatives. The Think Tank will be utilised to facilitate partnerships and networking opportunities to expand the reach of the project to other geographies, governments, institutions and communities of practice.

More details on the Think Tank members' involvement in dissemination and communication activities are outlined in [Deliverable 5.1 "Think Tank Terms of Reference"](#).

4.1.7 SCIENTIFIC DISSEMINATION

Open access national and international articles will be submitted by scientific partners in reputable journals. Results will be disseminated as quickly as possible, but only upon having shared the intent to publish with all other partners, and meeting considerations for potential contributions within the Consortium. Partners will present the project findings in relevant scientific conferences where possible. All partners adhere to the guidelines for open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their result, detailed in the GA.

The project coordination has drafted a Publication Policy and shared it with the research organisations in the consortium in 2023.

KPI: 15+ popular articles and 15+ scientific articles

4.2 TOOLS

Flyers, banners and posters have been and will be developed with the FoodCLIC branding and disseminated online and at events. Audio-visual materials such as infographics, podcasts, and webinars will be utilised to engage audiences via all channels. The products will be shared with partners and where possible/relevant in formats allowing adaptation to local languages. The outcomes of the real-life interventions will be summarised in short videos/vlogs shared via YouTube.

KPI: 50+ infographics

KPI: 16+ Short videos/vlogs on YouTube, project website; audience 5,000+

5. KEY PRODUCTS

The below table lists key products for communication and dissemination throughout the project.

Work package / product / Responsible	Audience	KPI	Due month
WP2 / Report on facilitators of, and barriers to development and implementation of evidence-based and integrated food policies and planning frameworks/ SURREY / D2.10	Direct stakeholders (- general public), adopters of strategies	200+ downloads / users / visits	M6
WP2 / Report on effective strategies to enhance access to sustainable and healthy food / SURREY / D2.6	Direct stakeholders (-general public), adopters of strategies, national, European and international stakeholders	200+ downloads / users / visits	M24
WP1 / Online toolkit for guidelines and tools for mappings, real-life interventions, RMDE framework and training / VU / D1.7	Direct stakeholders (-general public), adopters of strategies, national, European and international stakeholders	300+ downloads / users / visits	54
WP4 / 4 policy briefs / ICLEI ES / D4.6	National, European and international stakeholders, direct stakeholders (-general public)	Audience 5,000+	54
WP5 / 30 Practice abstracts / ICLEI ES / (D5.8 & D5.13)	Direct stakeholders (-general public), adopters of strategies, national, and European stakeholders.	30 uploads to EIP-AGRI	10 by M18 - 20 by M54
Presentations 15+ at international conferences	National, European and international stakeholders, direct stakeholders	Audience 750+ (50 per event); 80+ at events in the partner city-regions, audience 10,000+	
WP5 / Knowledge Hub	Direct stakeholders (-general public), adopters of strategies, national, European and international stakeholders.	Shared with at least 2,500 ICLEI, 141 Metropolis, 50 EMA and 60 MedCities members	54

ANNEX

Annex 1: History of changes from D5.2 to D5.7

<p>Chapter 1: BACKGROUND</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of context on 'First new updated version of the C&D plan' • Updated background information with more elaborated information on Broadening, Exploitation & Advocacy with reference to the Broadening process, the exploitation and advocacy plans. 	<p>February 2024</p>
<p>Chapter 2: BASICS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated links to reference(s) • Addition of Annex 2 • Addition of chapter 2.2 "BRANDING APPLIED: EXAMPLES" • Alignment of TERMINOLOGY section with glossary of Deliverable 2.2 and with evolved project language/ terms. 	<p>February 2024</p>
<p>Chapter 4: TOOLS AND CHANNELS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sub-section 4.1.1: Updated information on website (inclusion of links and explanations). • Sub-section 4.1.2: Updated information on social media with extended elaboration on LinkedIn incl. relevant hashtags + accounts • Sub-section 4.1.2: Updated list of relevant external and project partners' profiles • Sub-section 4.1.5 Updated overview of key events • Sub-section 4.1.6: Inclusion of reference to Deliverable 5.1 "Think Tank Terms of Reference"; multipliers added 	<p>February 2024</p>

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